

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SCHOOL CLIMATE AND TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

School climate refers to the quality and atmosphere of life that the school provides to all the stakeholders. A school is expected to provide conducive physical, intellectual, emotional, and social environment to children for their holistic development. School climate helps in providing a nurturing environment for the development of students' scholastic achievements, and psychological wellbeing, which shapes their future life. Job satisfaction is the level of happiness employees feel with their job. It is a positive emotive response one experiences while doing the assigned job. It is a multifaceted construct comprising workers' contentment with their job, happiness they derive from spending their time, energy and skills at work.

The study tried to study the relationship between school climate (SC) and job satisfaction (JS), teachers' perception about SC and JS, and compare the difference on perceptions of SC and JS across different demographic variables. It is a descriptive study with a sample size of 50 teachers in Mumbai area. The tools for the SC and JS were constructed and validated by the researcher. The data was collected online as well as offline. It was observed that SC and JS showed positive significant correlation. The teachers in Mumbai perceived SC and JS to be high, and the parameters of SC and JS to be equally important. The categories of Age and Gender did not differ in the perception of SC and JS. Teachers with higher qualifications, teaching higher level classes, and having more than 10 years of teaching experience have significantly higher scores on SC. Teachers with higher qualifications, and teaching higher level classes, have significantly higher scores on JS. Hence the school management has to maintain the school climate more open, democratic and free from other intervening things. When the teachers derive job satisfaction, it will reflect on schools' overall performance as well.

Keywords: # School Climate, # Job Satisfaction, # Professional Qualifications, # Teaching, # Performance

Introduction:

School climate refers to the quality and atmosphere of life that the school provides to all the stakeholders. It is the social atmosphere and the learning environment designed by the teachers and management with a purpose of offering different experiences, and imbibing values by the students. It aims at giving a caring and safe atmosphere to young budding minds and bodies. A school is expected to provide conducive physical, intellectual, emotional, and social environment to children for their holistic development. Positive school climate attends to the developmental needs of the children. It influences students' wellbeing and accomplishments in their life. School climate is the outcome of overall atmosphere that the school provides, which arouse feelings about and attitude towards the institute. School climate is an important consideration in school management.

Research has frequently shown that school climate helps in providing a nurturing environment for the development of students' scholastic achievements, and psychological wellbeing during their schooling years, which will shape their future life, (Ortega, R., Sanchez, Ortega R. J., & Viejo, 2011, as cited in NSCC, 2007). School climate is a multidimensional construct that includes physical, intellectual, social, emotional, and academic dimensions designed to nurture a student's personality.

The graduating students' outcome measures in terms of knowledge, skills and personality are closely linked to the quality of education they get in the school. The school complex is not just the building and infrastructure, but the human resources that shape the future generations in the schools. Educators are the pillars of any educational institution. Loukas (2007) has observed that quality school climate greatly helps 'at-risk students' in adjustment issues. How does the school climate impact students' development? What role does teachers' job satisfaction and commitment play in students' growth and development?

Job satisfaction reflects in the level of happiness employee feels with work profession. It is a positive emotive response one experiences while doing the assigned job. It is a multifaceted construct comprising workers' contentment with their job, happiness they derive from spending their time, energy and skills at work. Edwin A. Locke (1976), has defined job satisfaction as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences". When the job fulfills employee's monetary, mental, cognitive, social, and emotional wants and expectations, the employees get satisfaction from their jobs. For job satisfaction alignment between the personal and professional goals happens seamlessly.

If teachers are to deliver to the best of their ability, then they should be doing their job passionately, which underscores the importance of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction in turn comes from the environment which the schools provide them to discharge their duties diligently. Many schools complain about high teacher attrition and low morale, which result in poor student performance and damage the school's reputation. Hence it is imperative to maintain healthy working conditions, so that the teachers give their best shot in the school.

One of the important factors is school climate in which the students and teachers operate daily. If these interactions have to result into expected outcomes, the school leadership has to provide conducive environment, which boils down to maintaining favourable and positive school climate. Positive school climate will provide supportive working conditions to teachers and students both; and will motivate to do better in promoting growth.

Need for research:

School branding is linked to the effectiveness, well-being, and satisfaction of its teachers. Despite its significance, the relationship between school climate and teachers' job satisfaction remains less explored in many educational settings in India, especially in different types and levels of schools. This study will be beneficial to all the stakeholders to elevate the standard of the school, enhance quality of education, and most importantly educate the future generations of Indian citizens.

Objectives:

The present research was conducted

1. to study teachers' perception about the school climate and their own job satisfaction
2. to study the relationship between school climate and job satisfaction
3. to compare the difference in teachers' perception of the different parameters of SC
4. to compare the difference in teachers' perception of the different parameters of JS
5. to compare the difference in teachers' perception of the SC across different demographic variables
6. to compare the difference in teachers' perception of the JS across different demographic variables

Variables:

School Climate was measured on five parameters – Work Environment and Culture (WEC), Workload and Responsibilities (WR), Professional Growth and Recognition (PGR), Autonomy and Empowerment (AE), Compensation and Job Security (CJS).

Job Satisfaction was measured on five parameters – Safety and Well-being (SWR), Relationships and Collaboration Teaching (RCT), and Learning Environment (LE), Leadership and Voice (LV) and Resources and Environment (RE).

Demographic variables: Age, Gender, Teaching Experience, Professional Qualifications (Diploma, Graduate, Post Graduate) and Level of Teaching (Primary, Secondary, Higher Secondary).

Review of Literature:

School climate is the value and type of life the school provides. It depends on the stakeholders' experiences of school environment, and echoes the customs, vision, mission, objectives, values, relationships, instructional experiences, and school hierarchical systems. A sustainable and productive school climate fosters scholars' progress, and knowledge necessary for a creative, contributing and rewarding life in a democratic social order.

Based upon the extant research National School Climate Council, NSCC (2007) finalized 'Safety, Teaching and Learning, Interpersonal Relationships, Institutional Environment, and Leadership and Efficacy' as the five major domains of School Climate.

(Image Source: <https://schoolclimate.org/>)

School climate has been examined by researchers with reference to student variables like perception, scholastic achievement, emotional development and many such variables; teacher variables like professional development, job satisfaction, personal wellbeing, work life balance and more such ones, and societal variables like civil society, democratic behaviour, global citizenship and similar ones. Educational research has constantly verified that positive school climate is related to academic success, and positive youth development.

Loukas (2007) observed that students' perceptions of school climate are related to their behavioural and emotional problems. Understanding the psychological processes that trigger this relationship is important in developing effective strategies to improve school climate.

Good and healthy school climate endorses a positive relationship with the school, and guards students from negative implications. In other words, quality of school climate impacts learners' feelings of connectedness to the school and, in turn, the extent of this relationship predicts students' upcoming actions and emotional state (Menon, 2022). Published research literature is available to demonstrate how school connectedness and relationships impact the school climate and consequent student development.

Job Satisfaction:

Job Satisfaction comprises several key components that influence collectively employees' feelings about their jobs. Different researchers have identified number of overlapping factors. Spector (1997, as cited in Pavitra, 2022) has listed 14 common parameters for job satisfaction: Appreciation, Communication, Co-Workers, Fringe Benefits, Job Conditions, Nature of Work, Organization, Personal Growth, Policies and Procedures, Promotion Opportunities, Recognition, Security, and Supervision.

Employee job satisfaction encompasses more than just the individual employee, but equally the organization. It affects its overall health and effectiveness. If the employees are satisfied and happy, they will contribute for the growth and development of the organization they work for. Moreover, they develop loyalty towards the organization with full commitment.

Singh & Jain (2013) have described behavioural characteristics of satisfied employees. They are more productive, dedicated and strive to achieve excellence. Hence, they do not quit the organization. They display loyalty and commitment. Their approach to work is constructive and supportive. These employees resolve the conflicts easily by mutual understanding. The absenteeism and attrition rates are minimal. They provide excellent customer service and try to retain them as loyal customers.

Job satisfaction is categorized into intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. Intrinsic satisfaction stems from the type of work that the employee does, whereas extrinsic comes from rewards, recognition or work culture. The job satisfaction is a matter of personal as well as organizational success, as it is the employees who make the organization's success operational.

Relationship of School Climate and Job Satisfaction:

The positive relationship between school climate and job satisfaction can lead to reduced teacher stress and improved overall well-being. Studies consistently show a positive correlation between a supportive and healthy school environment and teachers feeling more content and motivated in their roles.

Relationship between school climate and teachers' job satisfaction was studied by different researchers across the globe. These studies conducted in different countries have found a statistically significant positive relationship between these two variables. This conclusion was arrived at by Treputtharatam & Tayiam (2013, Thailand), Li (2018, 23 countries database), Ghavifekr, & Pillai, (2016, Malaysia), Ross (2019, USA), Zakariya (2020, Norway), Ciavaldini-Cartaut, & Blaya, (2020, France), Marinette, Bahtilla & Hui, Xu. (2021, China), Akinnola & Oredein (2021, Nigeria), Yuan & Chayanuvat (2022, Thailand), Otrębski, (2022, Poland), Heinla & Kuurme, (2022, Estonia), Fang & Qi, (2023, China), Sahyunu, Ashadi, Bormasa, Supriatna, & Mutmainnah, (2023, Indonesia), Treputtharat & Noori, Said, Orfan, & Mohd Anis (2023, Afghanistan), Ningtyas, (2024, Indonesia), Nigeria, Mebrate & Lemma, (2024, Ethiopia), Yiming, L., Yan, L. & Jinsheng, Z. (2024, China), Meditamar (2024, Indonesia), Istiqomah, Neti Karnati, & Rugaiyah. (2024, Indonesia), Xia, Fan, Bai, Zhang, & Wen (2024, China), Soe, & Alegado, (2024, Japan, Korea, Finland, the United States of America (USA), and Australia), Erdem & Koçyiğit (2025, Türkiye).

Research done in Indian counterpart support these conclusions, (Basak & Ghosh, 2011; Bhattacharya & Mukherjee, 2011; Jenitta & Saminathan, 2013; Dutta, & Sahney, 2016; Sridevi & Amuthavalli, 2019; Maiti, 2020; Kumar, D., Kumar, N., & Jasvirkaur, 2021; Parua, 2021; Deb & Roy Choudhuri, 2023; Venkatesh, Kannan, Goswami, Prabhu Sahai, Burbure & Gomathi, 2023; Pal, Dey, & Roy, 2024; Madhu, & Sharma, 2024; Shallurani & Manminderkaur, 2024).

Few researchers have studied this relationship with a mediating variable; like Teachers' Self-Efficacy (Zakariya, 2020; Fang & Qi, 2024; Ningtyas, 2024, Meditamar, 2024); Teacher Motivation (Erdem & Koçyiğit (2025); Occupational Stress and Emotional Labour (Wei, Yuchen, Jingyu, Qingyi, & Yue, 2024); and Psychological Well-Being (Yiming, Yan, & Jinsheng, 2024). These research findings throw light on the complex relationship between the school climate and teachers' job satisfaction; and the interplay of different mediating variables therein. It may be surmised that the number of studies conducted in India are less in comparison with the different parts of the world. Moreover, the studies conducted are localised. So, the researcher chose Mumbai city as the study area.

H1: From the literature above, it is hypothesized that there is a significant relationship between school climate and teachers' job satisfaction.

Following additional hypotheses were formulated for the study, based upon additional variables. Due to scant published research evidence about the parameters of SC and JS, Null Hypotheses were framed.

H2: There is no significant difference among different parameters of SC among teachers.

H3: There is no significant difference among different parameters of JS among teachers.

H4: There is no significant difference among the SC scores across different categories of demographic variables, viz. Age, Gender, Teaching Experience, Professional Qualifications and Level of Teaching.

H5: There is no significant difference among the JS scores across different categories of demographic variables, viz. Age, Gender, Teaching Experience, Professional Qualifications and Level of Teaching.

Methodology:

The study has employed a descriptive correlational study design, with a sample of 50 teachers from Mumbai area. The geographical area and small sample were chosen for sake of ease of data collection. Voluntary response sampling (non-probability) was used to collect the online as well as offline data. The tools for the School Climate and teachers' Job Satisfaction were constructed by the researcher and were content validated using expert judgement. The School Climate tool had 25 items measuring five behavioural parameters – Work Environment and Culture (WEC), Workload and Responsibilities (WR), Professional Growth and Recognition (PGR), Autonomy and Empowerment (AE), Compensation and Job Security (CJS). Each parameter had five items for its measurement. The teachers' Job Satisfaction tool had 25 items measuring five behavioural parameters – Safety and Well-being (SWR), Relationships and Collaboration Teaching (RCT), and Learning Environment (LE), Leadership and Voice (LV) and Resources and Environment (RE). Each parameter had five items for its measurement. Both the SC and JS were five-point rating scales, where ratings varied from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The Cronbach Alpha for School Climate (SC) for was 0.857, and for Job Satisfaction (JS) was 0.849. The study employed a non-probability voluntary response sampling technique. Data were collected using a validated rating scale administered using Google Forms. The data was coded and curated for further analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The data has been analysed using Cross Tabulations, Pearson Correlation and ANOVA with Post Hoc Analysis (Tukey's HSD) techniques. The data was analysed using SPSS V25.

This section precedes with the sample distribution as per the Demographic variables and later testing of the hypotheses.

The sample distribution (Demographic variables) is given in Table 1 below. This composite Table gives the sample categorized across all the demographic variables.

Table 1 Sample Distribution (Demography Analysis)

Crosstabulation of Experience * Gender * Age * ProfQual * LevelTeaching						
Level of Teaching	Professional Qualification	Age	Experience	Gender		Total
				Male	Female	
Primary	B.Ed	25 to 34	Less than 5 Yrs	4	2	6
			6 to 10 Yrs	0	1	1
		35 to 44	Less than 5 Yrs	2	0	2
			6 to 10 Yrs	0	1	1
			More than 10 Yrs	0	2	2
		45 to 54	More than 10 Yrs	0	1	1
		55 to 60	More than 10 Yrs	0	1	1
Secondary	D. Ed	45 to 54	6 to 10 Yrs	1	0	1
	B.Ed	25 to 34	Less than 5 Yrs	2	2	4
			6 to 10 Yrs	1	1	2
		35 to 44	Less than 5 Yrs	1	1	2
	M.Ed	35 to 44	6 to 10 Yrs	0	1	1
		45 to 54	More than 10 Yrs	0	1	1
55 to 60		6 to 10 Yrs	0	1	1	
Higher Secondary	D. Ed	35 to 44	More than 10 Yrs	0	1	1
	B.Ed	35 to 44	6 to 10 Yrs	1	0	1
			More than 10 Yrs	0	1	1
		45 to 54	More than 10 Yrs	1	1	2
	M.Ed	25 to 34	6 to 10 Yrs	2	0	2
			More than 10 Yrs	0	1	1
		35 to 44	6 to 10 Yrs	1	1	2
			More than 10 Yrs	1	1	2
		45 to 54	6 to 10 Yrs	0	1	1
			More than 10 Yrs	0	2	2
55 to 60		6 to 10 Yrs	1	0	1	
	More than 10 Yrs	5	3	8		
Total				23	27	50

Figure 1 Demography wise Sample Distribution Percentage

Interpretation: The sample has 54% females and 46% males; 52% have completed their graduation and 48% are postgraduates. With reference to teaching experience 44% have more than 10 years of experience, and 48% teach higher secondary classes.

Objective 1: To study teachers’ perception about the School Climate and their own Job Satisfaction

Table 2 below presents how teachers perceive school climate and job satisfaction

Table 2: Perception of school climate and job satisfaction

Category	School Climate (%)	Job Satisfaction
Low	2 (4%)	3 (6%)
Moderate	12 (24%)	6 (12%)
High	36 (72%)	41 (82%)
Total	50 (100%)	50 (100%)

Interpretation: The Table shows that 72% teachers perceive SC as high and only 4% find it to be low. 82% teachers are highly satisfied, and only 6% have low JS. It may be observed that the teachers in Mumbai perceive the SC and JS to be high.

Objective 2: To study the relationship between school climate and job satisfaction

H1: There is a significant relationship between school climate and teachers’ job satisfaction.

Table 3 Correlation between school climate and their own job satisfaction

Correlation	School Climate & Job Satisfaction
Pearson Correlation	0.798**
Sig. (1-tailed)	0.0001
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)	

Interpretation: The Pearson Correlation is 0.798 which is significant at 0.01 level and is positive. As the p-value is less than 0.05, NH is rejected. It indicates a strong positive correlation, suggesting a close linear relationship between two variables where an increase in one is associated with a strong increase in the other. It means that both the variables are interdependent and their values move in the same direction. Higher the value of SC, significantly higher is the value of JS.

Objective 3: To compare the difference in teachers’ perception of the different parameters of SC

H2: There is no significant difference among different parameters of SC among teachers.

Table 4 presents teachers’ perception of SC across five parameters (WEC, WR, PGR, AE, and CJS).

Table 4 Comparison of parameters of SC using One Way ANOVA

Comparison of Parameters of School Climate					
Source	Sum of Squares SS	Degrees of Freedom df	Mean Square MS	F statistic	p-value
Treatment	26.376	4	6.594	0.3236	0.862
Error	4,992.30	245	20.3767		
Total	5,018.68	249		NH Retained	

Interpretation: The SC scale has Work Environment and Culture (WEC), Workload and Responsibilities (WR), Professional Growth and Recognition (PGR), Autonomy and Empowerment (AE), Compensation and Job Security (CJS) as the parameters. The Table 4

shows that the p-value corresponding to the F-statistic of One-Way ANOVA is higher than 0.05 (p-value = 0.862, df = 249), suggesting that the difference among the mean scores of these five parameters is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence NH is retained. It may be surmised that teachers perceive these five parameters of SC equal.

Objective 4: To compare the difference in teachers’ perception of the different parameters of JS

H3: There is no significant difference among different parameters of JS among teachers.

Table 5 presents teachers’ perception of JS across five parameters (SWR, RCT, LE, LV, and RE).

Table 5 Comparison of parameters of JS using One Way ANOVA

Comparison of Parameters of Job Satisfaction					
Source	Sum of Squares SS	Degrees of Freedom df	Mean Square MS	F statistic	p-value
Treatment	26.456	4	6.614	0.4041	0.8056
Error	4,009.96	245	16.3672		
Total	4,036.42	249		NH Retained	

Interpretation: The JS scale has Safety and Well-being (SWR), Relationships and Collaboration Teaching (RCT), and Learning Environment (LE), Leadership and Voice (LV) and Resources and Environment (RE) as the parameters. The Table 5 shows that the p-value corresponding to the F-statistic of One-Way ANOVA is higher than 0.05 (p-value = 0.8056, df = 249), suggesting that the difference among the mean scores of these five parameters is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence NH is retained. It may be surmised that teachers perceive these five parameters of JS equal.

Objective 5: To compare the difference in teachers’ perception of the SC across different demographic variables

H4: There is no significant difference among the SC scores across different categories of demographic variables, viz. Age, Gender, Teaching Experience, Professional Qualifications and Level of Teaching.

Table 6 and Table 7 present the ANOVA between SC and Demographic Variables, Age and Gender respectively.

Table 6 ANOVA Age and SC

Age & SC					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2141.226	3	713.742	1.927	0.138
Within Groups	17038.154	46	370.395		
Total	19179.380	49		NH Retained	

Table 7 ANOVA Gender and SC

Gender & SC					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	331.235	1	331.235	0.844	0.363
Within Groups	18848.145	48	392.670		
Total	19179.380	49		NH Retained	

Interpretation: The Tables 6 and 7 show that the p-value corresponding to the F-statistic of One-Way ANOVA for Age and SC (p-value = 0.138, df = 49); and for Gender and SC (p-value = 0.363, df = 49). Both being higher than 0.05, the Null Hypothesis is retained for these two demographic variables, suggesting that the difference among the mean scores of SC for the different categories of Age and those of Gender is not significant at 0.05 level.

Tables 8 to Table 10 present the ANOVA between SC and Demographic Variables, Professional Qualifications, Teaching Experience, and Level of Teaching respectively. Table 11 presents the Post Hoc analysis of the Demographic Variables where significant differences were observed across pairs.

Table 8 ANOVA Professional Qualifications and SC

Qualification & SC					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2823.174	2	1411.587	4.056	0.024
Within Groups	16356.206	47	348.004		
Total	19179.380	49		NH Rejected	

Table 9 ANOVA Teaching Experience and SC

Experience & SC					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2551.490	2	1275.745	3.606	0.035
Within Groups	16627.890	47	353.785		
Total	19179.380	49		NH Rejected	

Table 10 ANOVA Level of Teaching and SC

Level of Teaching & SC					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7164.755	2	3582.378	14.014	0.00002
Within Groups	12014.625	47	255.630		
Total	19179.380	49		NH Rejected	

Interpretation: Tables 8 to 10 show that the p-value corresponding to the F-statistic of One-Way ANOVA for Qualifications and SC (p-value = 0.0.24, df = 49); for Teaching Experience and SC (p-value = 0.035, df = 49); and for Level of Teaching and SC (p-value = 0.00002, df = 49). The p-value of each of the three demographic variables is less than 0.05. Hence, the Null Hypotheses are rejected for these three variables. It is concluded that the difference among the Mean scores of SC for the different categories of Professional Qualifications, and those of Teaching Experience, and Level of Teaching is significant at 0.05 level.

The results of these three variables were subjected to Post Hoc Analysis (Tukey’s HSD) and are presented in Table 11 below.

Table 11 Post Hoc Test for the significance across pairs of Demographic Variables & SC

Tukey HSD				
School Climate		Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.
More than 10 Yrs	Less than 5 Yrs	15.94805*	6.43051	0.043
Secondary	Primary	25.83333*	6.28982	0.0005
Higher Secondary	Primary	27.04167*	5.37686	0.00002
M.Ed	B.Ed	14.90559*	5.40400	0.022
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.				

Interpretation: The difference in the mean scores of SC between Teaching Experience (More than 10 years and Less than 5 years); Level of Teaching (Secondary and Primary, and Higher Secondary and Primary); and Professional Qualifications (M. Ed and B. Ed) is significant at 0.05 level, as the p-values of all these four pairs (0.043, 0.0005, 0.00002 and 0.022 respectively) are less than 0.05. Hence the NH is rejected for these pairs.

The Mean of the More than 10 years' Experience > Less than 5 years' experience; the Mean of the Secondary Level of Teaching > Primary Level; the Mean of the Higher Secondary Level Teaching > Primary Level; and the Mean of M. Ed. as the Qualification > B. Ed. Qualification. It is therefore, concluded that Teachers with higher qualifications, teaching higher level, and having more than 10 years of teaching experience have significantly higher scores on SC.

Objective 6: To compare the difference in teachers' perception of the JS across different demographic variables

H5: There is no significant difference among the JS scores across different categories of selected demographic variables, viz. Age, Gender, Teaching Experience, Professional Qualifications, and Level of Teaching.

Tables 12 to 14 present the ANOVA between JS and Demographic Variables, viz. Age, Gender and Teaching Experience respectively.

Table 12 ANOVA Age and JS

Age & JS					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1939.864	3	646.621	2.067	0.118
Within Groups	14392.216	46	312.874		
Total	16332.080	49		NH Retained	

Table 13 ANOVA Gender and JS

Gender & JS					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	34.035	1	34.035	0.100	0.753
Within Groups	16298.045	48	339.543		
Total	16332.080	49		NH Retained	

Table 14 ANOVA Teaching Experience and JS

Experience & JS					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1513.976	2	756.988	2.401	0.102
Within Groups	14818.104	47	315.279		
Total	16332.080	49		NH Retained	

Interpretation: Tables 12 to 14 show that the p-value corresponding to the F-statistic of One-Way ANOVA for Age and JS (p-value = 0.118, df = 49); for Gender and JS (p-value = 0.753, df = 49); and for Teaching Experience and JS (p-value = 0.102, df = 49).

These values being higher than 0.05, the Null Hypotheses are retained for these three demographic variables, suggesting that the difference among the mean scores of JS for the different categories of Age, Gender and those of Teaching Experience is not significant at 0.05 level.

Tables 15 and 16 present the ANOVA between JS and Demographic Variables, viz. Professional Qualifications, and Level of Teaching respectively. Table 17 presents the Post Hoc analysis of the Demographic Variables where significant differences were observed across pairs.

Table 15 ANOVA Professional Qualifications and JS

Qualification & JS					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2415.010	2	1207.505	4.078	0.023
Within Groups	13917.070	47	296.108		
Total	16332.080	49		NH Rejected	

Table 16 ANOVA Level of Teaching and JS

Level of Teaching & JS					
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5673.282	2	2836.641	12.508	0.00004
Within Groups	10658.798	47	226.783		
Total	16332.080	49		NH Rejected	

Interpretation: The Tables 15 and 16 show that the p-value corresponding to the F-statistic of One-Way ANOVA for Professional Qualifications and JS (p-value = 0.023, df = 49); and for Level of Teaching and JS (p-value = 0.00004, df = 49). The p-value of each of these two demographic variables is less than 0.05. Hence, the Null Hypotheses are rejected for these two variables. It is concluded that the difference among the Mean scores of JS for the different categories of Professional Qualifications, and those of Level of Teaching is significant at 0.05 level.

The results of these two variables were subjected to Post Hoc Analysis (Tukey's HSD) and are presented in Table 17 below.

Table 17 Post Hoc Test for the significance across pairs of Demographic Variables & JS

Tukey HSD				
Job Staisfaction		Mean Differenc	Std. Error	Sig.
Secondary	Primary	24.10714*	5.92430	0.001
Higher Secondary	Primary	23.52381*	5.06439	0.00008
M.Ed	B.Ed	13.81469*	4.98480	0.021
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.				

Interpretation: The difference in the mean scores of JS between Level of Teaching (Secondary and Primary, and Higher Secondary and Primary); and Professional Qualifications (M. Ed and B. Ed) is significant at 0.05 level, as the p-values of all these three pairs (0.001, 0.00008, and 0.021 respectively) are less than 0.05. Hence the Null Hypotheses for these pairs are rejected.

The Mean of the Secondary Level of Teaching > Primary Level; the Mean of the Higher Secondary Level Teaching > Primary Level; and the Mean of M. Ed. as the Qualification > B. Ed. Qualification. It is therefore, concluded that Teachers with higher qualifications, and teaching higher level, have significantly higher scores on JS.

Discussion of Results:

The result regarding the correlation between SC and JS is consistent with the research studies mentioned in the review of literature in India and abroad.

The present study has examined the difference in the scores of SC and JS among different categories of each of the demographic variables. Age did not show significant difference in the scores of SC and JS between different subgroups. This result is not consistent with Li (2018)

who conducted study globally with TALIS (2013) data base; and concluded that older teachers have higher JS than the young teachers. It also concluded that teachers with more working experience have lower level of job satisfaction than teachers with less working experience. This may be because of the difference in the SC the teachers experience. Moreover, the tools to measure JS were different in both the studies.

The present research's finding concurred with Li (2018), which states that teachers' gender is not significantly associated with their job satisfaction; but was not consistent with the result by Mebrate & Lemma (2017), which concluded that the Male teachers were more satisfied than the Female teachers. The difference in results may be due to the Gender wise M/F percentage sample distribution; which was 54/46 in the present study, and 70/30 in case of Mebrate & Lemma (2017); the geography of the research (SIDAMA Zone is a Tribal area in SW Ethiopia) for the other study, whereas Mumbai (Megalopolis area) for the present research; and the difference in the items of the tools chosen for measuring Job Satisfaction.

As there are not many published studies for comparison, it is suggested that more studies be undertaken for analysis of demographic variables.

Conclusion:

SC and JS are positively correlated. They are interdependent; and higher the value of SC, significantly higher is the value of JS. More than 75% teachers feel that SC is very good in their institutes and are highly satisfied in their jobs. It may be concluded that the teachers in Mumbai perceive the SC and JS to be high. The teachers perceive the five parameters of SC scale (WEC, WR, PGR, AE, and CJS), and the five parameters of JS scale (SWR, RCT, LE, LV, and RE) as equally important.

Teachers of different Age groups and Gender do not differ in their perception of SC and JS. Teachers of different categories of Professional Qualifications, Teaching Experience, and Level of Teaching significantly differ in their perception of SC and JS. Teachers with higher qualifications, teaching higher level, and having more than 10 years of teaching experience have significantly higher scores on SC. Teachers with higher qualifications, and teaching higher level, have significantly higher scores on JS.

Limitations:

The data was collected from few school teachers in Mumbai. Taking into account a small sample size (50) and the geography of the sample, the results have limited generalizability. The analysis of school climate and job satisfaction with regards to the demographic variables is

indicative of the trend, which however, commands further in-depth studies, for better research insights.

Recommendations:

Research studies have shown that the school climate impacts job satisfaction; which in turn affects the teachers' performance. Adeyemi, (2008), Adejumobi, and Ojikutu, (2013), Faremi, and Jita (2019), Wolomasi, Asaloei, and Werang (2019), Baluyos, Rivera, and Baluyos (2019), Lai Eng Fei, and K Han, (2020), Akinnola, and Oredein, (2021), Bentil, (2021), and Satorre, (2022) have conducted research in different parts of the world and concluded the positive significant relationship among these three variables, indicating job satisfaction is as a mediator. Hence, it is recommended that the school management has to make a conscious effort to maintain the school climate more open, democratic and free from other intervening things. Teachers should be given academic freedom to experiment different teaching learning techniques focussing on students' development. When the teachers derive job satisfaction, it will reflect on schools' overall performance as well.

The teachers who are more experienced should coach or mentor the new entrants in the field of education and help them understand their role in student development.

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